

ASYMMETRY AND KURTOSIS COEFFICIENTS

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ANNOTATION.

Integrator multipliers while functions integration and their common amounts in finding is used . That's two in practice , functions and their variables analysis in achieving , in systems and another mathematician in the models use studied .

Key words : Integrator multipliers , differential equation , full differential .

ANNOTATION.

The article examines the use of asymmetry and skewness coefficients in data analysis, precision, and comparison of distributions Integrating multipliers are used to integrate functions and find their totals. Both of these applications are used in the analysis of functions and their variables, in systems and other mathematical models. .

Enter

$$M(x, y)dx + N(x, y)dy = 0 \text{ (1)}$$

in appearance the left side of Eq something $u(x, y)$ of the function complete differential , that is

$$du = M(x, y)dx + N(x, y)dy$$

if so _ equation full differential equation is called .(1)

equation full differential equation to be for

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial x}$$

a must execution need _ Full differential equation from the definition $du = 0$ is , from this $u(x, y) = C$ come output (C optional unchangeable). $u(x, y)$ function to find for y the immutable that we count , then $dy = 0$ from being $du = M(x, y)dx$ will be The last one equality x according to if we integrate ,

$$u = \int M(x, y)dx + \varphi(y)$$

equality harvest will be The last one equality y according to we differentiate and the result $N(x, y)$ to we equate because $\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = N(x, y)$ was _

$$\int \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} dx + \varphi'(y) = N(x, y)$$

or

$$\varphi'(y) = N(x, y) - \int \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} dx$$

will be The last one equality y according to integrated , $\varphi(y)$ the we find :

$$\varphi(y) = \int \left(N(x, y) - \int \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} dx \right) dy + C$$

So by doing

$$u(x, y) = \int M(x, y) dx + \int \left(N(x, y) - \int \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} dx \right) dy + C$$

to the result have we will be

$$M(x, y)dx + N(x, y)dy = 0$$

differential of Eq right side something of the function full differential has been situation we looked of this equation right side something of the function full differential don't be . Some cases so $\mu(x, y)$ function choose get possible is given _ the equation that's it to the function when multiplied by , its left side something of the function full differential to be can _ Harvest done differential of Eq common the solution With initial given of Eq common the solution one different will be Such $\mu(x, y)$ to the function given of Eq integrator multiplier is called Integrator multiplier to find for , given the equation for now unknown has been μ to multiplied by

$$\mu M(x, y)dx + \mu N(x, y)dy = 0$$

the equation we can The last one equation full differential to be for

$$\frac{\partial(\mu M)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(\mu N)}{\partial x}$$

equality appropriate to be need _ From this

$$\mu \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} + M \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial y} = \mu \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} + N \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial x}$$

being _

$$M \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial y} - N \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial x} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \right)$$

will be The last one the equation μ to will be

$$\frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \mu}{\mu \partial y}$$

that it was for

$$M \frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial y} - N \frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y}$$

will be

General without μ x, y to dependent, ie $\mu(x, y)$. Given equation only x

to depends integrator to the multiplier have if $\frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial y} = 0$ being

$$N \frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{d \ln \mu}{dx} = \frac{\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x}}{N} \quad (4)$$

will be Differential equation only y to the variable depends integrator to the

multiplier have if $\frac{\partial \ln \mu}{\partial x} = 0$ being

$$\frac{d \ln \mu}{dy} = \frac{\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y}}{M} \quad (5)$$

will be In these cases, equations (4) and (5). directly integrated

$$\mu = e^{\int \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) / N dx}, \mu = e^{\int \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \right) / M dy}$$

integrator multiplier we find In this case, ratios (4) and (5) are the first without y to the variable depends non-existent, the second without x to the variable depends didn't happen integrator of multipliers existence means

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